

Reevaluating Capital Punishment And Psychosis: How Sane Must We Be To Qualify For Execution

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You have been assigned juror in each of the following cases and your responsibility is to decide which of these guilty suspects is sane enough to qualify for the death penalty, and which may be suffering from a mental health impairment that will qualify for conditional release after years of psychiatric treatment.

In your first case as a juror, you learn that suspect, Lisa Montgomery, befriended a 23-year-old pregnant woman, strangled her with an electric lamp cord then proceeded to cut the woman's baby girl out of the womb only to find that during the first few inches of this violent evisceration her victim awoke from the pain and began screaming. Montgomery then returned to strangling her victim, this time to death, finished removing the baby, and proceeded home with her new daughter.

In your second case as a juror you learn that suspect, Andrea Yates, decided that she could no longer deal with the stress of raising her five small children, so she proceeded to chase them through the house, the children screaming and fleeing from their mother in terror and attempting to hide in closets and under beds while she methodically drowned each in the bathtub, one child at a time.

As a juror, you must now decide which suspect seems sane enough to know right from wrong and thus face the death penalty, and which suspect was incapable of understanding the heinous nature of their crime and should be given compassion and psychiatric care. One suspect will be given the death penalty and one will be given conditional release after treatment. If you are struggling with your decision in these two egregious criminal cases, you're not alone. Unfortunately, there is no simple answer when we as a society adopt the role of judge, jury, and executioner by evaluating a criminal's state of mind at the time of the crime. The larger question here--Do we as a people possess the insight and wisdom necessary to accurately judge when it is appropriate to take someone else's life?

Lisa Montgomery was executed by lethal injection. Andrea Yates was not. Andrea was given psychiatric treatment and the possibility of a conditional release set for one day in the future. Lisa's life was ended at the stroke of a gavel. Each case leaves behind immense familial destruction, broken hearts, and ethical questions. Within each of these two cases, a large swath of society called for "revenge killing" while others demanded "compassion." Each defense presented evidence of a psychotic episode or a dissociative state of delusion resulting in an inability to know right from wrong. As judge, juror, and executioner, we must now ask ourselves, when is a murderer "sane enough" to qualify for execution, and when is one "sick enough" to qualify for treatment?

Lisa Montgomery remained on Terra Haute's infamous death row since 2001 until she was executed at 1:15 AM on January 13, 2021. She was the first female federal prisoner to be executed since 1951. Interestingly, her execution took place just days after the insurrection on the Capital, and at the height of the holiday COVID-19 surge while hospital intensive care units were overflowing with dying patients. Montgomery's execution in such a volatile case and at such a volatile time shines a harsh light on the continuing pursuit of the death penalty and "revenge killing."

Some Surprising Statistics

Of the world's 195 nation-states, the United States is one of 48 nations that still cling to this practice and one of only 18 nations carrying out scheduled executions every year for the preceding five years. Along with Japan, Taiwan, and Singapore, the United States is one of 4 advanced democracies and the only western nation that applies the death penalty regularly. Though public support for the death penalty has plummeted from 78% in 1996 to 54% in 2018, the practice is still administered in 28 states, as well as all federal territories and it is sanctioned under military tribunal.

Without explanation or rationale, Attorney General William Barr, on July 25, 2019, and during the COVID-19 pandemic, restarted executions within the federal system after a 16-year hiatus. The term "Trump Spree" described the administration's unprecedented push of 13 executions during Trump's lame-duck period, the most of any outgoing President in 130 years. Lisa Montgomery was executed only 8 days before Trump left office. Dustin Higgs' execution was scheduled just 5 days before the inauguration. Daniel Lewis Lee, on July 14, 2020, became the first convict to be executed by the federal government since 2003. In the weeks leading up to his execution, he and others were required by the prison system to wear a mask and social distance when being moved around on death row.

In 1972, Congress banned executions based on the Eighth Amendment's "cruel and unusual punishment" clause. There had been no executions between 1967 and 1977. But in 1976, after the introduction of lethal injection, an alternative to the "less humane" methods of electrocution, gassing, long-rope hanging, and firing squad, the option for capital punishment was reinstated. Since 1976, 7,800 defendants have been sentenced to death and more than 1,500 have been executed. Over those years 172 individuals were exonerated and removed from death row, however as of 2020, there remains 2,591 defendants languishing on death row, a traumatic experience that many describe as worse than death itself. Since then, 22 states have abolished the practice of capital punishment, with Michigan and Vermont abolishing it permanently.

In 2020, only 5 states, Alabama, Georgia, Missouri, Tennessee, and Texas continued executions. From 1970 to 2021, there were 1529 executions, 1349 by lethal injection, 163 by electrocution, 11 by gas inhalation, 3 by firing squad, and 3 by hanging (yes, states still execute by firing squad and hanging). Under then Governor George W. Bush, Texas which leads the nation in State-sanctioned executions with 576, more than a third of all executions nationwide, proclaimed that death row inmates must complete all appeals within a 7-year window so to reduce the excessive cost of the legal process.

The Financial Side of Capital Punishment

Studies show that death penalty cases cost 70% more than the cost of a comparable non-death criminal case. California estimates that its current death row system costs annually 137 million dollars, and with proposed reforms, that cost is expected to skyrocket to \$232.7 million compared to the annual cost of a mere lifetime in prison which costs the state \$11.5 million overall. Prosecution costs to adjudicate a death penalty case is 48% higher than the average cost of a standard criminal trial. New York estimates that it invests more than 8,000 hours in public defender representation compared to less than 180 hours for non-death criminal defense. Just the cost of staffing alone for death row officers is seven times more expensive. Between 1978 and 2011, California death penalty prisoners have cost the state \$1 billion, and with the addition of outside defense and appellate costs, \$3 billion over that same period. Finally, the cost of death itself has gone up since 2011 when a single dose of lethal injection was \$83.55. Today in states like Virginia, that same dose is over \$16,500 per injection due to European chemical suppliers, as the main source, refusing to contribute to this controversial practice.

The average cost to taxpayers for every death row inmate is approximately \$8.2 million and most will languish there for an average of 11 years. Eventually, the Antiterrorism and Effective Death Penalty Act was signed into law by President Bill Clinton in 1996 designed to further streamline the appeal and execution process. Virginia maintains the shortest duration, 8 years, from time of conviction through execution. There still exists a problem with "botched executions." It is estimated that 34 of the previous 749 executions between 1977 and 2001 or 4.5% resulted in unanticipated problems that caused unnecessary agony to the prisoner. Some in society might say, "so be it." The Eighth Amendment says otherwise.

Total executions in 2020 however, were notably fewer, and the lowest count since 1991. This decrease was likely the result of scheduling complications and court delays due to COVID-19. It was COVID-19 that played a role in delaying the execution of Lisa Montgomery when her attorney became ill. Ironically, Montgomery was being held at a women's psychiatric institution receiving treatment for mental health while she awaited execution.

Back to Montgomery

As shocking as Montgomery's actions may sound, her crime was by no means unique. Such crimes have come to be defined by a specific term: "fetal abduction." These are homicides in which a pregnant woman is murdered to provide a baby for another woman, usually one who is infertile. The unborn infant is often violently removed from the mother's body. Shockingly, there have been 18 such cases in recent years, none until Montgomery received the death penalty. Of the cases, 4 victims and 13 infants survived.

In April of 2004, Montgomery befriended Bobbie Jo Stinnett at a dog show. Both women shared an interest in dog breeding and had exchanged messages through an online board. Stinnett maintained a website called Happy Haven Farms to promote a dog breeding business located in her home in Missouri. When Stinnett became pregnant in 2004, she shared the news with her online community which included Montgomery.

In the Spring of 2004, Montgomery began telling family, friends, and online acquaintances that she too was pregnant. This proved to be biologically untenable. Montgomery had undergone tubal ligation nearly 10 years earlier, a practice that cauterized her fallopian tubes. Her second husband at the time, Kevin Montgomery, and her children were not aware of the sterilization. Montgomery acted pregnant and wore maternity outfits. Her former husband and his wife along with others who knew of the sterilization accused Montgomery of lying. She warned that she would prove them wrong.

Using an alias, Montgomery contacted Stinnett on December 15th, 2004, by instant message. Stinnett had a litter of puppies for sale advertised on her website and Montgomery expressed interest in purchasing one. That day, Montgomery arrived concealing a knife and a strangling cord. She took Stinnett by surprise. A struggle ensued and Montgomery overpowered the younger woman, first strangling her unconscious then cutting her womb open to remove the baby. As previously described, Stinnett regained consciousness just as Montgomery was slicing into her abdomen. Montgomery then returned to strangling Stinnett until she was finally asphyxiated. Montgomery then proceeded to remove the fetus, slicing Stinnett's womb open with the kitchen knife and removing a baby girl that, save for a small cut over one eye resulting from the grotesque violence perpetrated on the mother's abdomen, was perfectly healthy.

Montgomery took the baby and drove to Topeka calling her husband when she arrived. She explained that she had gone into labor while Christmas shopping and that she delivered the baby at a women's clinic in Topeka. She asked her husband to pick her up and drive her back to Missouri with the new infant. The rest of that day Montgomery continued to claim the baby was hers while at the same time, Stinnett's family found the 23-year old's body, cut open and lying in a pool of blood. When authorities confronted Montgomery the very next day her story fell apart and she confessed to the murder. As a juror, can you separate yourself from this gruesome event? Would you describe Montgomery as sane or insane? Was she delusional? Did she understand right from wrong?

While in custody, Montgomery presented a weak defense for her acts. She first claimed amnesia but there existed evidence of premeditation and planning that countered that claim. Montgomery had searched for information online relating to pregnancy, cesarean section, and field delivery of babies. It was also learned that she had previously faked pregnancy on four other occasions. Cases involving a psychological preoccupation with an imaginary pregnancy is a malady known as pseudocyesis, in which an individual presents with symptoms of pregnancy even though they are not real. Experts testified that she did not appear to suffer from the strict definition of this condition.

Montgomery's personal history was nevertheless tragic. As a child she had been physically and sexually abused by her stepfather and brothers. Her parents divorced when she was sixteen and Montgomery claimed her mother engaged her in acts of prostitution. At age 18, she married her stepbrother Carl Boman and had four children with him. It was in 1990 that Montgomery underwent the tubal fulguration procedure, which she claimed was forced upon her by her mother and her husband. She divorced Boman in 1998. In 2000, she married her second husband, Kevin Montgomery. She claimed to be pregnant on multiple occasions but would not allow her husband to accompany her on visits to her physician. That doctor later testified that he treated Montgomery for ankle pain and a cold, and nothing related to prenatal care. Montgomery later told her husband that the baby had died and that she had donated the body to science.

In 2004, Montgomery became involved in a custody battle with her first husband, Boman. Boman learned of her faked pregnancy claims and threatened to expose her and to use the information against her at the custody proceedings. This, prosecutors suggested, was a motive behind the offense. Their theory was that Montgomery needed to prove Boman wrong to win custody of her children.

Mental and Emotional Capacity

At the center of every capital punishment consideration is a discussion surrounding "rational choice." Judiciaries throughout history were tasked with evaluating motive and cognitive awareness. Reaching back to the first capital cases against women, in 1632 the first woman executed in the United States was Jane Champion, convicted and hanged for "infanticide." Most women sentenced to capital punishment in the 17th and 18th centuries were executed for child murder. Female executions fall far short of male executions by approximately 1 in every 285. The only time in United States history where more women were executed than men was during the Salem witch trials of the 17th century where women accounted for 80% of all executions.

Another factor for consideration when evaluating an individual's mental and emotional capacity is age. In the United States, juvenile executions were finally abolished as recently as 2005. The last juvenile to be executed was Scott Hain in Oklahoma in 2003 at age 17. It was only through a societal plea to provide juveniles with treatment rather than retribution that our nation moved the needle

away from the arms of the young and the mentally ill. Although an increased number of cases are being reversed as a result of advancements in DNA, most defense attorneys move for an insanity plea.

Faced with the harsh facts of the case and the prosecution's intention to seek the death penalty for their client, Montgomery's legal counsel opted to present a mental disability defense. Her attorney hired Dr. Ruben Gur, Ph.D. who was prepared to testify based on neuropsychological testing, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and positron emission tomography (PET Scan). Gur's defense suggested that Montgomery likely suffered from brain structural and functional abnormalities that could induce pseudocyesis. These abnormalities could be the result of traumatic brain injury (TBI) suffered as a child. This was a risky defense because it required absolute proof of physical rather than psychiatric damage.

While the court acknowledged that the beatings and sustained sexual abuse she suffered as a child, including gang rapes and being prostituted by her mother, were serious factors, it was concluded that these arguments "read like a clemency petitioner [and thus the] court [was] not the proper forum in which to request clemency which [lay] in the exclusive province of the Executive Branch, not the Judicial Branch." Advocates of "therapeutic jurisprudence," rather than "retributive jurisprudence," claim that factors such as those presented in Montgomery's case are essential for jurors at the time of sentencing. This advocacy fell on deaf ears most likely due to the egregious nature of the crime and society's disdain for the violence perpetrated against the victim in this case.

Dr. Gur's testimony went to the core of the Montgomery defense which was competency. Was Lisa Montgomery sufficiently capable of understanding the consequences of her actions or was she far too seriously impaired and unstable to make rational choices? This crucial question should always remain at the center of any discussion of capital punishment. Yet, all too often, public sentiment and media exposure drive the adjudication process. The more heinous and egregious a crime appears to society, the more influence society has over the court in its evaluation of sociopathic senselessness and the failed socialization involved in its commission.

Between Punishment and Compassion

It is often society and not merely the court which weighs heavily on whether a just response should be strictly punitive. With consideration for both the Andrea Yates case involving post-partum stress, and the Lisa Montgomery case involving emotional abuse, society often drives the court to choose between punishment and compassion, between forgiveness and revenge. Do we revert to the Old Testament's "an eye for an eye" or do we "turn the other cheek" and move to a higher plane of civilized order and social cohesion?

Appeal processes for clemency in capital cases are often time-intensive and exceedingly expensive. In addition, they are also driven by public sentiment and media blow-back, not to mention political influence. Montgomery's clemency appeal was 8,000 pages. A question of judicial overhaul may require our system to consider the human rights of the accused despite public sentiment over the egregious nature of the crime. This might begin with the elimination of the "perp-walk" (guilty before proven innocent) and continue with systemic reform throughout every facet of punitive retribution. The federal government currently enjoys a 98.5% conviction rate due to an overwhelming number of plea agreements that result from the threat of an imposed "trial penalty" for those who wish to raise a jury.

Concerning Lisa Montgomery's appeal, the appellate court considered several factors, chiefly whether Montgomery was truly a victim of TBI and whether she was competent to stand trial. "Most

courts have been unresponsive to TBI claims...[Federal courts have] found that [defendants] did not establish that there is [any] national consensus against executing individuals who are criminally responsible and competent, even if they suffer from traumatic brain injury." (Lynch, Perlin, Cucolo) In Montgomery, the appellate court saw the significance of the brain imaging scans but excluded the evidence. Dr. George Woods, an expert in neuropsychiatry, evaluated Montgomery in January of 2021 for the stay of execution appeal and determined that "Lisa Montgomery [was] unable to rationally understand the Government's rationale for her execution." (Montgomery v. Warden, Application for Stay of Execution Petition For Writ of Habeas Corpus (January 12, 2021, N*2: 21-CV-00020-JH-DLP, p.76-77))

Other issues were considered such as derogatory statements made by the prosecutor regarding the character testimony of Montgomery's oldest daughter: "After all that, [Montgomery] drags [her] kids into court here to testify in this high-profile case in front of all these people, and puts them through this again, and victimizes them again in front of the whole world...She's a good mom? Most of us, if we had children [and]we were involved in a situation we would want them a thousand miles away from this. We wouldn't make them come to court and testify." (Id.)

Despite this prosecutor's disdain for her children's character testimony, there would seem no legal basis for the exclusion or disparagement of the children's opinion of their mother or their desire not to see her executed. However, in our adversarial and predatory legal system, it is a prosecutorial strategy to destroy any remaining vestige of humanity and decency in those offenders we mean to put to death--a philosophic approach borrowed from military training in which soldiers are taught to dehumanize the enemy so they become easier to neutralize.

Another factor that was considered for appeal was whether the charge of murder in the course of kidnapping was an accurate definition of Montgomery's offense since the murder occurred first and was independent of the kidnapping of the fetus. This claim was easily dismissed, and it was typical of defense counsel grasping at straws during an emotionally charged proceeding.

The reality is that TBI, psychological factors, PTSD, and intellectual disabilities play a significant role in human violence yet as a society we often ignore the science and fail to consider all mitigating circumstances that affect or impair our judgment. In recent years advancements in science have provided us an opportunity to appreciate the effect trauma has had on altered thinking, and specifically repeat trauma resulting from a sports injury.

Traumatic Brain Injury

It is estimated that about 12% of all adults suffer from a chronic condition resulting from Traumatic Brain Injury or TBI. Variations of the disease include Chronic Traumatic Encephalopathy (CTE) which has been linked to erratic behavior. Men are twice as likely to develop the syndrome as women, and 43% of those suffering from a brain injury experience long-term disability.

Football players like Aaron Hernandez, Junior Seau, and Dave Svenson are just a few who have displayed impaired judgment. Hernandez committed murder and then killed himself while in prison; Seau and Svenson were each suicide. Postmortem autopsies revealed severe brain damage from repeated concussions. Hernandez's condition was the worst. Doctors said he had brain damage typically found in 60-year-old ex-football players or boxers like Mohammad Ali. Our sports are violent, our crimes are violent, and our institutions seem bent on fighting violence with violence.

Consider the case of long-haul trucker Alfred Bourgois. In 2004, Bourgois killed his two-year-old daughter in front of her mother by slamming the little girl's head against the dashboard of his truck during a fit of anger. Later, it was determined that the child had been routinely beaten, tortured, and burned. Bourgois and his wife kept the infant in the rig while they made deliveries to Corpus Christi Air Naval Base. They kept the child on a training toilet seat which she inadvertently overturned causing her father to fly into a rage.

Because the murder took place on federal property, a military base, Bourgois was sentenced to death by a federal court. Post-trial medical and psychological examination of Bourgois found that he was suffering from severe deficiencies in mental function, scoring near the line of intellectual disability on IQ tests. The Government considered him competent enough to hold the trucking job even though the company Bourgois worked for provided a significant support system for intellectually challenged employees. As a juror, ask yourself, could you show compassion for his intellectual deficiencies and avert from the death penalty in exchange for finding him treatment? Or would you commit him to death for the carnage he inflicted on his daughter?

One of the 2021 executions was that of Corey Johnson a crack cocaine trafficker who killed seven people in 1990. Like Bourgois, Johnson also suffered from intellectual deficiencies repeating the third and fourth grades and showing no capacity to grasp basic concepts such as the date of his birthday. Johnson could neither tell time nor recite the 12 months of the year, and cognitive testing suggested that he simply could not understand the difference between right and wrong. He was executed, nevertheless.

Then there was the case of Lezmond Mitchell, a Native American Navajo man who killed a Navajo woman, Alyce Slim, and her nine-year-old granddaughter with the help of an accomplice in 2003. He was also found to be severely mentally handicapped, so much so that the Navajo Nation insisted he not be executed. The Navajo community is philosophically opposed to the concept of "revenge killing," and insists that it does not, as a people, accept revenge as a response to violence. The Federal courts, however, do. Mitchell was sentenced to die by lethal injection even though the crime transpired on Navajo lands and under Navajo Tribal Law. The decision by the federal court to commit Mitchell to death was imposed against the wishes of the entire Navajo Nation, including family members of the victims.

It seems, however, that our criminal court system and their imposed death sentences are also arbitrary. Not all high-profile crimes result in the death penalty. John W. Hinckley, who shot President Reagan, seriously wounded Press Secretary James Brady, a Capitol police officer, and a Secret Service agent in 1981, was recently released following his treatment within a psychiatric facility. During that term, Hinckley was permitted to visit with his mother at her home from time to time and received extensive psychiatric care and counseling. Two other Presidential assassins, Lynette "Squeaky" Fromme and Sara Jane Moore are each out of prison following psychiatric treatment for mental illness. It was Hinckley's case that led to the Insanity Defense Reform Act of 1984. Hinckley was eventually released in 2016 and currently lives with his mother.

Andrea Yates' case led to the "McNaughten Rules" which expanded the criteria for "reason of insanity," and it was Yates' case that brought about the "Irresistible Impulse Test" to evaluate sociopathology and cases involving "dissociative states of delusion." Social violence, however, continues to plague our culture on many levels. Abolitionists of the death penalty continue to

advocate for a system of therapeutic justice, for an end to our authoritarian, retributive legal approach.

One would believe that the death penalty is introduced only in the most heinous of crimes such as first-degree murder, however, this is not the only crime that invokes capital punishment. There are sixteen aggravating factors to be applied to murder when seeking a death sentence. Three of them are linked exclusively to narcotics trafficking. Florida and Missouri call for the death penalty in large-scale drug trafficking cases. North Carolina and Texas in the early 2000s attempted to pass legislation within their respective states to permit the death penalty for child predators even when no death transpired. That legislation was eventually reversed under Supreme Court authority. The criteria for the death penalty has evolved since America's first execution.

History Lessons

Looking back in history, the first person to be executed (by hanging) was a 17-year-old boy in the British Colony of Plymouth in 1642. His crime? Sodomy with livestock. In later years, hanging cattle rustlers was a widespread practice throughout the 19th century. Today, society struggles with the concept of "revenge killing." More people are asking what purpose execution serves in this enlightened age. Deterrence has already been ruled out. Many French news bulletins written during the time of the French Revolution described the spectacle of the public hanging for those caught stealing. Reporters would warn spectators to "mind the pick-pockets" that lurk in the crowd during the event. Studies show that the penalty of capital punishment is often the last thing one may consider during a crime of passion or an overt act of violence. Murder continues to display the lowest recidivism of all felony crimes.

The possibility of challenging the death penalty constitutionally became more realistic in 1958 with *Trop v. Dulles*. For the first time, the Supreme Court declared explicitly that the clause for "cruel and unusual punishment" must be drawn from "evolving standards of decency that mark the progress of a maturing society." But just how "evolved" are we at present? Is there truly a communal definition of "civility," and "decency?"

Of the current 62 death row cases pending within the federal system, and the approximate 1578 pending within the states, it is estimated that only about 6% of state cases and about 21% of federal cases will be overturned. Montgomery's attorney, Kelly Henry, on the night of Lisa's execution decried, "The craven bloodlust of a failed Administration was on full display tonight." Expecting the Trump Administration to offer a final reprieve, all hope was lost for Montgomery at 1:15 AM on January 13, 2021. The Biden Administration has pledged to place a moratorium on all future federal executions, but in Montgomery's case, neither Trump nor Barr would postpone the execution by the mere 8 days she needed to appeal to Biden.

Lisa Montgomery was asked if she had anything to say before the lethal injection was administered, any significant last words. Her reply was simply and sadly, "No." Facing the ultimate indignity at the hands of an uncaring, cruel, and bureaucratically vengeful legal system, what else was left for her or anyone to say? There are no last words, there is only action.

Sources: Lynch, Alison and Perlin, Michael L. and Cucolo, Heather: "Traumatic Brain Injury and The Criminal Trial Process"; DOJ.gov, United States Court of Appeals, Eighth Circuit; McNaughton Rules; Insanity Defense Reform Act; National Geographic, Feb. 2021; Lieberman, James, Columbia Law School/Temple Law Review; Espy File; Report by Amnesty International, Feb. 2021; Freedom, Eric, Death Penalty Reversals; CDC.gov; Chammah, Maurice/"Let God Sort Them Out"

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